

Magnetic Properties of Solid Solutions.

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Homogeneous crystals containing two salts mixed in indefinite proportions and formed in solutions containing a mixture of both salts were called "Mixed crystals" by Roozeboom (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1899, 30, 385) and named solid solutions by Van't Hoff (*Z. Phys. Chem.* 1890, 5, 322) because they showed great resemblance in their behaviour to ordinary liquid solutions, and obeyed the laws applicable to them. Doubts have been expressed by Kuster (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1895, 17, 367), Lehmann (*Ann. Physik*, 1894, 51, 67), Ruzicka (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1910, 72, 381) and Von Weimarn (*Kolloid Z.*, 1910, 7, 35) as to whether it is right that these isomorphous mixtures should be considered as solid solutions at all. This position cannot be maintained any longer, for it has been shown by Bruni and Meneghini (*Atti. R. Accad. Lincei.*, 1911 (5), 20, i, 671, 927), Sirovich and Cartoceti (*Gazzetta*, 1922, i, 52, 436) and Desch (*Brit. Assoc. Reports*, 1912, 348) that diffusion, a process regarded as characteristic of the gaseous state and that of solution, takes place not only in the case of crystalline metals, but also in the case of mixed crystalline salts like sodium chloride—potassium chloride, potassium chloride—potassium bromide, etc. Moreover, Tamman (*Nachr. Ges. Wiss. Göttingen*, 1916, 119) has shown that when mixed crystals of gold and copper, or of gold and silver, are treated with reagents which are solvents for one of the components, they do not behave as if they were heterogenous mixtures. Finally, x-ray examination of the mixed crystals of potassium bromide—potassium chloride and of potassium bromide—ammonium bromide, etc., by Vegard and Schjelderer (*Physikal. Z.*, 1917, 18, 93) and by Vegard (*Z. Physik*, 1921, 5, 393) alone has shown that they behave as single entity and not as if they were composed of thin laminae of the individual salts. In the crystal lattice of the mixed crystal, the vicarious elements replace each other atom for atom.

Moreover, in these too, like the liquid solutions many of the physical properties do not necessarily follow the mixture law. For example, it is a well known fact that electrical conductivity of solid solution is much smaller than that of the mechanical mixture of the two metals. Bruni and Meneghini (*Atti. Ist. Veneto*, 1911, ii, 71, 195), M. M. Papov, A. Bundel and V. Choller (*Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **147**, 302) have shown that heat of solution of solid solutions of potassium chloride—potassium bromide series is smaller than that of mechanical mixture of the two constituents. Freezing point curves of the solid solutions when plotted may be between the freezing points of the pure components or it may pass through a maximum or a minimum. H. Endo (*Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1925, **14**, 479) while studying the relation between the equilibrium diagram and magnetic susceptibility in binary alloys, has shown that though the magnetic susceptibility concentration curve of the mixture of two metals remains straight yet that of a solid solution becomes curved, but no definite relationship between magnetic susceptibility and any other property of solid solution has been arrived at.

In order to determine such a relationship it is necessary that an accurate magnetic study be made of the simpler solid solutions. In the present investigation attention has been restricted to a close examination of the following types of solid solutions.

(1) Those in which the components are simple, stable crystalline salts.

(2) Those which form unbroken series of mixed crystals.

(3) Those which are either truly isomorphous or their freezing point curves pass through a minimum.

Solid solutions of potassium permanganate—potassium perchlorate, potassium chloride—sodium chloride, potassium bromide—potassium chloride and potassium bromide—sodium bromide have been examined over the entire range of the composition.

EXPERIMENTAL.

The salts from which these solid solutions were prepared, were the purest obtainable and further purified by fractional crystallisation from water and analysed before use.

Potassium permanganate decomposes on melting. It was necessary, therefore, to make solid solutions of potassium permanganate

and potassium perchlorate by precipitation from aqueous solutions. The method used was that described by Fock (*Z. Kryst.*, 1897, 28, 337). A solution of the mixture in different proportions in water at a temperature slightly above that of the room, was cooled and vigorously shaken. The crystals that separated were quickly filtered off and dried with filter paper. These were kept in a vacuum desiccator till further use. Since only 2—3 per cent. of the substance in solution crystallised out, the composition of the solid solution can be considered to be constant. The samples got in this way were analysed for potassium permanganate volumetrically and potassium perchlorate when in small quantities by colorimetric method by F. L. Hahn (*Z. angew. Chem.*, 1926, 39, 451) and when in large quantities by the usual precipitation method.

In other cases as the pure components melt without decomposition, proper amounts of each were weighed, and were ground well in an agate mortar. Portion of the mixture was placed in a hard glass tube which was sealed and was heated in an electric furnace. When the mixture melted, the melt was cooled gradually by lowering the temperature of the furnace and finally kept for 6 hours at about 30-40° below the temperature of solidification. The melt was then quenched to the room temperature, for, otherwise if the molten mixture be cooled slowly after solidification the solid solutions decompose. The quenched mass was kept along with the mechanical mixture in a vacuum desiccator. The percentage composition of the constituents both in the mixture and solid solutions was determined by the usual method and the amounts of the constituents both in the solid solution and the mixture were found to be the same.

The magnetic susceptibility of solid solutions as well as of the mixtures was determined by a magnetic balance of the Wilson type (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1920, A, 96, 429). The substance contained in a small glass tube hooked to an arm of the very light glass system, was suspended in a non-homogeneous magnetic field by a fine quartz fibre. The force exerted by the field was balanced by the torsion of the suspension and read off from a graduated head. The susceptibility of the sample is calculated by the formula of Oxley (*Proc. Roy. Soc.*, 1922, A, 101, 264).

$$\chi = \frac{1}{M} \left[x_a M_a + (x_w m_w - x_a m_a) \frac{D - D_1}{D_2 - D_1} \right]$$

where x = susceptibility of the specimen,
 M = mass of the specimen in grams,
 x_a = specific susceptibility of air (210×10^{-7}),
 M_a = mass of air filling the same volume as the specimen,
 x_w = specific susceptibility of water,
 m_w = mass of water filling the same volume as the specimen,
 m_a = mass of air filling the same volume as water,
 D = torsion due to specimen tube specimen,
 D_1 = torsion due to specimen tube alone,
 D_2 = torsion due to specimen tube comparison substance
 (water).

Pure water, which has a mass susceptibility at ordinary temperatures of -7.2×10^{-7} (Wills, *Phys. Rev.*, 1905, 20, 158), was used as the comparison substance in all determinations.

Susceptibility of the pure salts.—The mass susceptibility of the salts from which the solid solutions were prepared are given in Table I, and for comparison the values from International Critical Tables are added.

TABLE I.

Salt.	Mass susceptibility $\times 10^7$.	International critical tables $x \times 10^7$.	Kiyoshi Kido $x \times 10^7$.	Bhatnagar-Mathur interference balance, $x \times 10^7$.
Potassium chloride	-5.049	-5.16	-4.81	-5.031
Sodium chloride	-4.888	-4.99	-5.06	-4.902
Potassium bromide	-3.702	-3.77	-4.04	-3.706
Sodium bromide	-3.568	-4.70	-4.20	-3.610
Potassium perchlorate	-2.877	—	—	—
Potassium permanganate	+1.82	+1.80	—	—

The susceptibility of the salts has been determined at various times by different workers and recently by Kiyoshi Kido (*Sci. Rep. Tohoku Imp. Univ.*, 1932, 21, 149). The values differ because the information about the purity and state of hydration of salts is insufficient. The values of these salts, therefore, were checked on the Bhatnagar-Mathur magnetic interference balance set up in this laboratory and the values obtained are given in the last column of Table I.

Potassium perchlorate—potassium permanganate system.—The change of susceptibility with composition of the solid solution and that of mechanical mixture is shown in Fig. 1 and the values are tabulated in Table II.

FIG. 1.
KMnO₄—KClO₄ System.

○ = Susceptibility of solid soln.
= „ „ „ mixture

TABLE II.

Specimen.	% of KMnO ₄ .	Mass susceptibility × 10 ⁷		Solid solution.
		Mechanical mixture.		
		Cal.	Observed.	
KMnO ₄	100	+1.80	+1.82	---
A	88	+1.256	+1.347	+1.321
B	74	+0.5987	+0.641	+0.632
C	60	-0.0588	No effect	No effect
D	39	-1.0451	-1.012	-0.95
E	27	-1.6088	-1.60	-1.60
F	14.6	-2.1912	-2.157	-2.172
G	5	-2.6421	-2.6401	-2.632
KClO ₄	0	—	-2.877	—

The susceptibility—composition curve for the solid solutions of potassium permanganate—potassium perchlorate follows practically a linear course like that of the mixture. Therefore the susceptibility of potassium perchlorate—potassium permanganate mixed crystals may be calculated approximately by the mixture law from the values of the constituents and the composition of mixed crystals.

Potassium chloride—potassium bromide, sodium chloride—Potassium chloride and potassium bromide—sodium bromide systems.—The susceptibility values for potassium chloride—potassium bromide, sodium chloride—potassium chloride, sodium bromide—potassium bromide solid solutions and those of mixtures are given in Tables III, IV and V. Curves have been plotted for the systems sodium chloride—potassium chloride and sodium bromide—potassium bromide and are shown in Figs. 2 and 3.

FIG. 2.
KCl-NaCl System.

FIG. 3.
NaBr—KBr System.

TABLE III.

Potassium chloride—potassium bromide System.

Specimen.	Mol. % KBr	Molecular susceptibility $\times 10^6$			Difference.
		Mechanical mixture. Calculated.	Observed.	Solid solution.	
KBr	100	...	-440.3
A	90	-433.93	-434.2	-434.9	0.7
B	80	-427.56	-428.3	-431.7	3.4
C	70	-421.19	-421.9	-428.3	6.4
D	65	-418.00	-417.7	-422.9	5.2
E	50	-404.0	-408.5	-408.8	0.3
F	35	-397.5	-395.5	-395.7	0.2
G	10	-382.97	-388.0	-383.1	0.1
KCl	0		-376.6		

TABLE IV.

Potassium Chloride—Sodium Chloride System.

Specimen.	Mol. % KCl	molecular susceptibility $\times 10^7$			Difference
		Mechanical mixture.		Solid solution.	
		Calculated.	Observed.		
KCl	100	...	-376.6
A	93	-370.2	-369.4	-370.1	0.7
B	80	-356.4	-357.5	-365.7	8.2
C	65	-344.71	-335.4	-360.0	20.6
D	50	-331.3	-325.4	-352.0	26.6
E	35	-316.8	-315.9	-338.6	22.7
F	20	-304.12	-303.5	-310.1	6.6
G	10	-295.06	-294.4
NaCl	0	...	-286.6

TABLE V.

Potassium bromide—Sodium Bromide System.

Specimen.	Mol. % of KBr.	Molecular susceptibility $\times 10^7$			Difference.
		Mechanical mixture		Solid solution.	
		Calculated.	Observed.		
KBr.	100		-440.3		
A	80	-425.66	-426.0	-437.2	11.20
B	70	-418.34	-418.2	-434.1	15.9
C	65	-414.68	-414.7	-432.0	17.3
D	50	-403.70	-407.0	-427.7	27.7
E	40	-396.90	-398.5	-417.5	19.0
F	35	-394.50	-396.0	-414.2	18.2
G	10	-374.42	-376.0	-388.7	12.2
NaBr	0		-367.1		

The susceptibility-composition curve of the solid solutions in case of potassium chloride—sodium chloride and potassium bromide—sodium bromide passes through a maximum and the maximum in both the cases is at 50% composition. The curve in the case of potassium chloride—potassium bromide is very slightly curved with a maximum at 70% composition potassium bromide.

Results.

From the results given in Tables I to V, we can arrive at the following conclusions: (1) the susceptibility-concentration curve of a system of solid solution may follow a linear course, or (2) it may pass through a maximum.

In potassium perchlorate—potassium permanganate system, which is a true isomorphous system, the susceptibility-concentration curve is practically a straight line. This is what is expected because the truly isomorphous substances are those in which the physical properties are continuous functions of the percentage composition of the constituents (Retger's law) and the magnetic susceptibility would thus naturally be expected to follow the Retger's law.

In potassium chloride—potassium bromide, sodium chloride—potassium chloride and sodium bromide—potassium bromide systems, it is found that the susceptibility concentration curve passes through a maximum. The maximum in the system potassium chloride—potassium bromide is at 70 per cent. molecular composition of potassium bromide and in the systems sodium chloride—potassium chloride, sodium bromide—potassium bromide, the maximum lies at 50 per cent.

If the freezing point curves for potassium chloride—potassium bromide (Amadori U. Pampanini: *Rend. Linc.*, 1911, (5), 20, ii, 572) potassium chloride—sodium chloride and potassium bromide—sodium bromide (Kurankow and Zemczuznyj, *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1907, 52, 186), systems be studied, they can be classed among that type of solid solutions in which the freezing point curve passes through a minimum, and that point in potassium chloride—potassium bromide system is at 70 per cent. molecular composition of potassium bromide and in sodium chloride—potassium chloride, potassium bromide—sodium bromide systems is at 50 p.c. molecular composition. Thus we observe that the solid solutions having percentage composition for which the melting point is a minimum, has the maximum magnetic susceptibility for that very composition. This fact is not true in case of salt solutions only but is also true of metallic solutions like that of copper-gold where we find that magnetic susceptibility-concentration curve has a maximum whereas the freezing point curve passes through a minimum.

This suggests a possible correlation of the heat of formation of different systems with the magnetic susceptibilities of the systems. For example, Table VI shows the heat of formation and the susceptibility of solid solution of that percentage composition which has a maximum value.

TABLE VI.

System.	Molecular per cent. composition.	Susceptibility curve.	Heat of formation.	Reference.
KClO ₄ -KMnO ₄	...	Linear	0 Cals.	Sommerfeld ¹
KCl-KBr	70 % KBr	Curved	220	Bruni and Amadori; ² M. M. Popov, A. Buedel and V. Choller. ³
KBr-NaBr	50 % KBr	Curved	1400	Kurnakow and Zemczuczni ⁴
KCl-NaCl	50 % KCl	Curved	2100	do

From the results tabulated above, it is clear that the greater heat of formation of the solid solution is synonymous with the greater magnetic susceptibility of the system. When the heat of formation of the system is zero, the susceptibility-concentration curve of that system follows a linear course.

1. *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1901, **36**, 754.
2. *Atti. Ist. Veneto.*, 1911, *ii*. 71, 51.
3. *Z. Phys. Chem.*, Ab. A., 1930, **147**, 302.
4. *Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1907, **52**, 186.

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